

WATERAGRI

D8.3: Policy Impact Strategy

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WP 8 Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation

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List of Abbreviations and Acronyms	
AGU	American Geosciences Union
CAP	Common Agricultural Policy of the European Union
EC	European Commission
EGU	European Geosciences Union
EIP-AGRI	European Innovation Partnership for Agricultural productivity and Sustainability
EU	European Union
DGs	Directorate General of the European Commission
HSE	Health and Safety Executive in the United Kingdom (Britain's national regulator for workplace health and safety. It prevents work-related death, injury and ill health.)
IAH	International Association of Hydrogeologists
M&E	Monitoring and Evaluation
MOOC	Massive Online Open Course
MSC	Most Significant Change approach
NGO	Non-Governmental Organization
ODI	Overseas Development Institute
RBM	Results-Based Management
RBMP	River Basin Management Plans
REF	Research Excellence Framework in the United Kingdom
RTZ	U.K.-registered mining company with important assets in natural resources and related industries
UK	United Kingdom
UN	United Nations
UNCBD	United Nations Convention on Biological Diversity
UN COP	United Nations Conference of Parties
UNFCCC	United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change
WFD	Water Framework Directive

1 The need for a policy impact strategy

This strategy intends to help making the projects’ research agenda and research findings relevant to policymaking in a way that has an impact¹ on how policy² is formed, implemented and understood. Whether and how this happens is something that the consortium can influence and manage:

“Non-academic research impact is about identifying the influences of research findings on policy, managerial and professional practices, social behaviour or public discourse. Such impact may be instrumental, influencing changes in policy, practices and behaviour, or conceptual, changing people’s knowledge, understanding and attitudes towards social issues.”

Davies, Nutley and Walter, 2005

Policy can be formed by various actors and be influenced through different means. Exemplary representation can be found in Figure 1 which also extend beyond the EU.

¹ Results-Based Management (RBM) uses the model *Inputs > Activities > Outputs > Outcomes > Impact*, where ‘outcomes’ refers to mid-term accomplishments, and ‘impacts’ refers to long-term results.

² A set of rules or norms governing behaviour in a particular area of activity - established by an organisation (the “policy-maker”) accepted as having authority to set such rules or norms. The basis of this authority is usually, but not universally, statutory in nature. It may also include authority to enforce the rules. (from: The University of Cambridge (2017))

c)

Types of influence	Indicators and tools
Expanding policy capacities	Developing new talent for research and analysis
	Improving data quantity and quality
	Enhancing knowledge of all actors to a level where decision-making can occur
	Improving capabilities of communication and understanding
	Creating an environment for actions whose impact is measured beyond the current policy cycle
	Providing opportunities for inter-, multi-, and transdisciplinary knowledge generation
Broadening policy horizons	Introducing new concepts to frame multi-actor interaction (e.g. debates, putting ideas on the agenda, stimulating public debate)
	Stimulating dialogue and interactions between decision-makers
	Fostering holistic views in researchers involved in policy-relevant research
Affecting policy regimes	Modifying existing policies or programmes
	Fundamentally re-designing policies or programmes
	Creating an environment where radical change is possible and feasible

Figure 1: Aspects of policy to consider in research projects (a) from: *The University of Cambridge (2017)*., (b) own representation, and (c) adapted from *Weyrauch et al. 2010*

Policy impact can be achieved through various means but is generally difficult to prove or track. Figure 2 shows four approaches to influence policy, namely: advising, advocating, lobbying and activism. WATERAGRI is a Research and Innovation Action funded by the European Commission. It is therefore strongly rooted in evidence and science, but intends to produce marketable products and services, thus also representing interests. As an advisory body or as part of an advisory body WATERAGRI will also contribute to policies by cooperation with the Commission or national governments, working directly on inside tracks drafting policy recommendations. At national level WATERAGRI intends to have an impact on a set of water and agriculturally related policies (see Annex 1: Policies, decrees, rules or laws that WATERAGRI could influence or be influenced at various levels for a list of national and local policies that WATERAGRI could influence).

Figure 2: Representation of different policy influencing techniques and approaches characterized by Start and Hovland, 2004.

2 Developing a policy impact strategy

This strategy document will base its work on the following definitions by [Hovland \(2017\)](#), with points 3–5 being critical for this strategy (points 1&2 are handled in WP9):

- 1) **Strategy and direction:** The basic plan that the research project/programme/institution is following in order to reach its intended goals.
- 2) **Management:** The systems and processes that the project/programme/institution has in place in order to ensure that the overall strategy is carried out and that high-quality policy research is produced (e.g., systems of peer/user review, quality assurance and planning cycles).
- 3) **Outputs:** The tangible goods and services that a research project/programme/ institution produces (e.g., Working Papers, journal articles, policy briefs, website, meetings, events and networks, tested and verified technologies and services; best practices).
- 4) **Uptake:** Direct responses to the research project/programme/institution (e.g., its research is mentioned in a government policy paper, on a range of websites and referred to in a newspaper article).
- 5) **Outcomes and impacts:** Changes in behaviour, knowledge, policies, capacities and/or practices that the research has contributed to, directly or indirectly (e.g., a change in government policy implementation, a change in working practices among NGO practitioners, a reduction of poverty in a certain area, strengthened livelihoods and strengthened civil society input into policy processes).

The WATERAGRI Policy Impact Strategy is based on the following process:

- 1) Rough literature review of different policy impact strategy handbooks and tools (see documents in reference list);
- 2) Agreement on outputs, outcomes and impacts of the project that the strategy should focus on by Task 8.3 members through a logframe;
- 3) Development of a first strategy, targeted policies, target policymakers and suggested implementation plan to be reviewed and vetted by all consortium members;
- 4) Consultation with all consortium members and comments on the implementation (timing of activities) and regular update; and
- 5) Development of a final strategy for final agreement by all consortium members.

3 Applying the policy impact strategy

This section sets forth the policies that the strategy intends to influence through the project, as well as stakeholders that could help doing so. It also describes a set of activities and benchmarks to achieve the following target:

WATERAGRI's goal is to influence EU-wide and EU-country-specific agricultural policy towards sustainable agricultural food production and ecosystems in line with European bio-economy. It intends to do so by providing evidence-based case examples of efficient water use and reduced pollution rates through efficient technological and other water and nutrient management options and a shift to a systemic approach in agriculture.

It needs to be noted that all ideas put forward in the following sections are based on the current knowledge of the consortium at the time of the writing of this strategy (July – Dec. 2020). We are conscious of the fact that a new EU government has taken charge in the past year and that the COVID-19 pandemic as well as further unknown factors are and can strongly influence shifts in the policy directions at international, EU and national levels. Regular updates of this strategy and in particular of the activities will ensure that the strategy remains valid throughout the course of the project.

3.1 Policies relevant to/for WATERAGRI

The WATERAGRI consortium undertook a first exercise in collecting international, European, and national policies that may be of relevance to be influenced or which will influence WATERAGRI (Annex 1: Policies, decrees, rules or laws that WATERAGRI could influence or be influenced at various levels). This exercise can be repeated and compared with for the mid-term review to account for significant changes (see Chapter 3).

3.2 Stakeholders that could influence policymaking identified in WATERAGRI

An initial stakeholder register was set up to support stakeholder engagement within and across the project (see also D1.1: Stakeholder Management Plan). Within this register different stakeholder categories³ give insight into potential stakeholders that may be directly addressed to support and drive policy impact of WATERAGRI results (see an overview per category and country in Table 1 and an initial indicative list under

³ The WATERAGRI Stakeholder register identifies 22 different stakeholder categories.

Annex 2: Initial indicative list of stakeholders that could influence policymaking). This list of stakeholders will be assessed and if needed revised for the mid-term review (see Chapter 3). Current stakeholder categories include: Policy makers at local level/municipalities, local water management organizations and water companies, policy makers at national level, and influencers at European level. Further categories could still be added. These stakeholders are considered as important actors to be actively involved in shaping future policies towards sustainable water and nutrient management and should therefore also be specifically considered in WATERAGRI activities with the objective of gaining them as partners.

Table 1: Overview of types of stakeholders named in the different WATERAGRI case study countries.

	Policy makers at local level/municipalities	Local water management organizations	Local agricultural management organizations	Policy makers at national level
Austria	4	1	2	1
Germany	-	-	1	-
Finland	-	1	1	-
France	1	2	1	3
Hungary	-	-	3	-
Italy	2	5	1	-
Poland	2	2	6	2
Sweden	2	1	1	-
Switzerland	2	2	2	1

3.3 WATERAGRI activities for policy impact

While the project sets out to achieve a number of objectives that contribute to outcomes and impacts, this logframe (Table 2) focuses on the project activities that lead to policy outputs, outcomes and eventually impacts (i.e. not all activities in the project lead to a policy output, outcome or impact). A number of these activities are also reflected in D8.1: Dissemination and Communication Plan in particular in Section 4: Dissemination Strategy. Therefore, processes for dissemination established in D8.1 will also be adopted for D8.3.

Table 2: Logframe defining activities, outputs, outcomes and expected policy impacts of WATERAGRI

Activity	Output	Outcome	Impact
High-quality scientific writing	Peer-reviewed journal articles in high impact journals	Expertise of consortium scientists and project results validated amongst scientific peers	
High-quality scientific work	Presentation (oral/keynote) at international scientific conferences (EGU, AGU, IAH, Wetpol, etc.)		
Written summaries of high-quality scientific work	Findings are provided to global report outlets such as the World Water Development Report, UN Environment Frontiers		

	Report, the Institute for Sustainable Development's Knowledge Hub (www.sdg.iisd.org) and others		EU-wide and EU-country-specific agricultural policies are adapted towards sustainable agricultural food production and ecosystems in line with European bio-economy
Oral summaries of high-quality scientific work	Presentation (oral/keynote) at global science-policy conferences and events (Stockholm Water Week, UN COPs, etc.)	Expertise of consortium scientists and project results validated with practitioners	and
Oral summaries of combined scientific work	Presentation of and consultation on overarching findings to local stakeholders of case studies including local practitioners		Agricultural water management and soil fertilisation challenges are solved in a sustainable manner to secure affordable food production in Europe for the 21st century.
Training on project solutions	Trained stakeholders (including researchers)		
Oral and written recommendations, guidelines and best practices	Use of easily digestible formats to disseminate knowledge on technical, political and managerial aspects for water and nutrient management		
Oral and written expert statements	Serving on expert boards and panels		
Written statements on Policies	Position papers on international, EU-level, national and local policies as appropriate		
Written statements on the (potential) policy relevance of project results	Policy briefs ⁴	Expertise of consortium scientists and project results presented to policy makers	
Written summaries of project results	Practice abstracts in EIP-AGRI ⁵ format		
Oral summaries of combined scientific work	Presentations of and consultation on overarching findings to local stakeholders of case studies including (local) policy-makers		
Easily digestible versions of the scientific content	Articles in popular press, blog posts, newsletters, vlogs, etc.	Expertise of consortium scientists and project results presented to all actors including the general public	

⁴ Policy and briefing papers should be assessed against different criteria than academic journal articles. Policy papers are written specifically for the purpose of using evidence to shed light on a policy area. Briefing papers are produced with the same purpose but may be much shorter (perhaps 1-6 pages). Young and Quinn (2002) argue that good-quality policy and briefing papers have three core components: (i) they say what the *problem* is; (ii) what the possible *solutions* are, including the author's preferred solution; and (iii) what policy *recommendations* follow from this.

⁵ European Innovation Partnership for Agricultural productivity and Sustainability (EIP-AGRI)

3.4 Suggested benchmarks

While not all activities of the 48 months of the lifetime of the project can be anticipated, this strategy presents below an initial idea of activities that are foreseen by the WATERAGRI partners at the point of writing this document (Table 3). Processes for collecting and planning activities will be followed as set out in D8.1: Dissemination and Communication Plan and D9.1: Project Management Procedures and Quality Plan. Care will be taken to attend meetings physically or virtually depending on future COVID-19 hygiene and safety measures.

Table 3: Suggested benchmarks for the delivery of the activities to achieve the desired output

Activity	Name of outlet (Tentative name of article/talk, journal, conference, etc.)	Delivered by whom (partner)	When	Output
High-quality scientific writing	40 peer-reviewed journals	Solution providers	M7 – M48	Peer-reviewed journal articles in high impact journals
High-quality scientific work	15 conferences and symposiums	Solution providers	M7 – M48	Presentation (oral/keynote) at international scientific conferences (EGU, AGU, IAH, Wetpol, etc.)
Written summaries of high-quality scientific work	5 inputs to global level reports	OULU with input from all	M 1 – 48	Findings are provided to global report outlets such as the World Water Development Report, UN Environment Frontiers Report, the Institute for Sustainable Development's Knowledge Hub (www.sdg.iisd.org) and others
Oral summaries of high-quality scientific work	5 inputs to global science-policy conferences	OULU with input from all	M 1 – 48	Presentation (oral/keynote) at global science-policy conferences and events (Stockholm Water Week, UN COPs, etc.)
Oral summaries of combined scientific work	At least @ the 4 workshops planned in WATERAGRI	TUDELFT	M1 – M 48	Presentation of and consultation on overarching findings to local stakeholders of case studies including (local) practitioners and policymakers
Training on project solutions	MOOC educational material for farmers' schools and higher education institutions	CDR BOKU ULUND, BOKU, UNIBO, USAL, UPWr, TUDELFT, UNINE and INRAE	M43-48 M43-48	Trained stakeholders (including researchers)
Oral and written recommendations, guidelines and best practices	10 videos Factsheets on technical solutions	CDR, INOSENSE OULU, VTT, FZJ	M1-48 M12 – 24	Use of easily digestible formats to disseminate knowledge on technical, political and managerial

	Serious game	TUDELFT	M1-48	aspects for water and nutrient management
Oral and written expert statements	5 statements on diverse boards	TBD	M1 -48	Serving on expert boards and panels
Written statements on Policies	5 statements on Policies and Policy updates	OULU, CER, CDR	M1 - 48	Position papers on international, EU-level, national and local policies as appropriate
Written statements on the (potential) policy relevance of project results	Roughly 3 Policy briefs that showcase summarized findings	OULU	M24-48	Policy briefs
Written summaries of project results	30 practice abstracts - see also plan in D8.1: Dissemination and Communication Plan	TBR-Regelsberger ALCN INRAE and others	M24, M48	Practice abstracts in EIP-AGRI format
Easily digestible versions of the scientific content	8 articles	INOSENSE with content from others	M1 - 48	Articles in popular press, blog posts, newsletters, vlogs, etc.

4 Monitoring impact and measuring success

Monitoring the impact and measuring the success of the activities is a major challenge as it does usually not belong to the standard repertoire of academic evidence tracking. Figure 3 provides some inspiration of the types of indicators that can be gathered.

Figure 3: Overview of types of policy impacts (from: The University of Cambridge (2017))

WATERAGRI operates on several levels from local, through national towards the supra-national. Advances to influence policies in the field of water, nutrient, and agricultural aspects may be at different levels of maturity in the different cases and countries. At the same time consortium members may be more or less aware of the influencers and lobby groups as well as advances in policy impacts within their countries and cases. We are therefore conscious of the fact that the monitored impact is a subjective reflection of the change felt by and through the consortium and the project. It may not be an objective reflection of policy advances in general.

Having highlighted the subjective bias, we suggest monitoring the impact of the project at three levels:

- 1) In consortium members own contributions;
- 2) At the local level;
- 3) At the overarching project level.

It is our hope and expectation that these varying viewpoints may diminish subjective biases without lessening the need to highlight individual successes.

4.1 Tactics to be used by consortium members on their own contributions

4.2 Impact Logs: Impact logs are used to keep track of some of the direct responses that the research outputs trigger, and this in turn informs evaluation. An impact log is a list of the informal feedback, comments, and anecdotes received from people who have encountered or used its research outputs. It is not a systematic way of assessing user perceptions; rather, it is a way of capturing the qualitative and non-systematic feedback on research outputs that would otherwise get lost. A template on how to capture those experiences can be found in Annex 1: Policies, decrees, rules or laws that WATERAGRI could influence or be influenced at various levels

Level	Country/region	Name of policy, rule, law or decree	Link (if available) to text
International	UN	United Nations Conference on Sustainable Development (Rio+20), "The Future We Want"	General Assembly resolution 67/290 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development
	UNFCCC	The Paris Agreement	https://unfccc.int/files/essential_background/convention/application/pdf/english_paris_agreement.pdf

	UNCBD	The Nagoya Protocol on Access and Benefit-sharing	https://www.cbd.int/abs/
EU	European Union	Proposal for a REGULATION OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL establishing the framework for achieving climate neutrality and amending Regulation (EU) 2018/1999 (European Climate Law)	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?qid=1588581905912&uri=CELEX:52020PC0080
	European Union	Common agricultural policy (CAP)	https://ec.europa.eu/info/food-farming-fisheries/key-policies/common-agricultural-policy_en
	European Union	The future CAP	https://ec.europa.eu/commission/sites/beta-political/files/budget-may2018-modernising-cap_en.pdf https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=COM%3A2018%3A392%3AFIN
	European Union	Effect of CAP on water	https://ec.europa.eu/info/food-farming-fisheries/key-policies/common-agricultural-policy/cmef/sustainability/impact-cap-water_en
	European Union	The EU water policy, eg. the regulation on water re-use	https://ec.europa.eu/environment/water/index_en.htm FIT4REUSE deliverable on “Inventory of the current legislative and policy frameworks addressing non-conventional water resources treatment and application” (to be made available by UNIBO in Dec. 2020).
	European Union	Commission Staff Working Document Agriculture and Sustainable Water Management in the EU	https://circabc.europa.eu/sd/a/abff972e-203a-4b4e-b42e-a0f291d3fdf9/SWD_2017_EN_V4_P1_885057.pdf
	European Union	Nitrates Directive	https://ec.europa.eu/environment/water/water-nitrates/index_en.html
	European Union	Drought mitigation	https://ec.europa.eu/environment/water/quantity/eu_action.htm https://ec.europa.eu/environment/water/quantity/building_blocks.htm https://europeansting.com/2020/07/21/european-union-policy-for-improving-drought-preparedness-and-mitigation/

National	Austria	Austrian Water Protection Law (Österreichisches Wasserrechtsgesetz (WRG 1959 in the actual version))	https://www.ris.bka.gv.at/GeltendeFassung.wxe?Abfrage=Bundesnormen&Gesetzesnummer=10010290
	Austria	National Water Management Plan 2021 (Nationaler Gewässerbewirtschaftungsplan 2021)	https://www.bmlrt.gv.at/wasser/wasser-oesterreich/plan_gewaesser_ngp/nationaler_gewaesserbewirtschaftungsplan-ngp/ngp_arbeitsprogramm_2018.html
	Austria	Guidelines for advisory services on water and soil protection by the Landwirtschaftskammer Österreich (Austrian Chamber of Agriculture)	https://www.lko.at/bodenwasser-schutz-beratung+2500+2515416
	France	Payments for ecosystem services (Paiements pour services environnementaux)	https://agriculture.gouv.fr/les-paiements-pour-services-environnementaux-en-agriculture https://www.actualitesdudroit.fr/browse/affaires/droit-economique/26550/paiements-pour-services-environnementaux-la-commission-approuve-le-regime-d-aide-aux-agriculteurs
	France	Nitrates and Water Directives adaptation	https://www.ecologie.gouv.fr/protection-ressource-en-eau
	Italy	Implementation of Directive 2007/60/EC on the assessment and management of flood risks (Decreto Legislativo 23 febbraio 2010 n. 49 Attuazione della direttiva 2007/60/CE relativa alla valutazione e alla gestione dei rischi di alluvioni. (GU del 2 aprile 2010 n. 77) Testo consolidato 2020)	https://www.minambiente.it/normative/dlgs-23-febbraio-2010-n-49-attuazione-della-direttiva-200760ce-relativa-alla-valutazione-e
	Italy	Environmental Norm (Norma in materia ambientale; Decreto Legislativo 152 del 03/04/2006)	https://www.minambiente.it/sites/default/files/dlgs_03_04_2006_152.pdf
	Italy	Water management plan of the Po River Catchment (Piano di Gestione del distretto idrografico del fiume Po. Comitato Istituzionale del 3 marzo 2016, deliberazione n.1/2016 (DPCM 27 Ottobre 2016))	https://pianoacque.adbpo.it/piano-di-gestione-2015/
	Poland	Set of strategic national documents currently under construction in the area of water management in agriculture	

4.3 Annex 2: Initial indicative list of stakeholders that could influence policymaking

Stakeholder Category	Country	Organization
Policy makers at local level/municipalities	Austria	Provincial Government of Lower Austria
	Austria	Chamber of Agriculture of Lower Austria
	Austria	Styrian Provincial Government (Austria)
	Austria	Chamber of Agriculture of Styria (Austria)
	France	Puisaye-Forterre Municipalities Federation for Water Management (Fédération des eaux de Puisaye-Forterre)
	Italy	Municipality of Ravenna (Comune di Ravenna)
	Italy	Region of Emilia Romagna (Regione Emilia Romagna)
	Poland	Regional Agricultural Advisory Centers
	Poland	Regional and local Self-governmental authorities (regions, counties, communities)
	Sweden	Swedish Board of Agriculture (Jordbruksverket)
	Sweden	Municipality of Eslöv (Eslövs kommun)
	Switzerland	Councillor Ins (Gemeinderat Ins)
	Switzerland	Councillor Epsach (Gemeinderat Epsach)
Local water management organizations	Austria	Hydraulic engineering official expert for the district of Weiz South
	Finland	Centres for Economic Development, Transport and the Environment (ELY-centers)
	France	Yonne Regional Agency of the government (Direction Départementale du Territoire)
	France	Regional water agency (Agence de l'eau Seine Normandie)
	Italy	Po River District Basin Authority (Autorità di bacino distrettuale del fiume Po)
	Italy	Energy Resource Environment Holdings Hera (Holding Energia Risorse Ambiente,)
Italy	Regional Union of Reclamation Emilia Romagna ANBI ER (Unione Regionale delle Bonifiche Emilia Romagna)	

	Italy	Renana Reclamation Consortium (Consorzio di Bonifica Renana)
	Italy	Iren S.p.A. (Società per azioni italiana, operante quale multiservizi) → Plastic sorting,
	Poland	Local Water Companies
	Poland	State Water Holding Polish Waters
	Sweden	Ekologigruppen – Consulting company in ecological matters
	Switzerland	Technical Commission Water of Pro Agricultura (Technische Kommission Wasser der Pro Agricultura)
	Switzerland	Water supply Grosses Moos (Wasserversorgung Grosses Moos (WAGROM))
Local agricultural management organizations	Austria	Styrian Farmers' Association
	Austria	Chamber of Agriculture Upper Austria energy and climate
	Finland	ProAgria – Expert services for rural entrepreneurs
	France	Yonne Chamber of agriculture
	Germany	Chamber of Agriculture North-rhine Westphalia (Landwirtschaftskammer Nordrhein-Westfalen)
	Hungary	Hungarian Irrigation Association
	Hungary	T-Markt Ltd.
	Hungary	MAGTÁR Ltd
	Italy	Regional federation (Federazione Regionale) Coldiretti Emilia-Romagna
	Poland	Agricultural Advisory Branch Office in Radom
	Poland	Lubelski Agricultural Advisory Service in Końskowola
	Poland	Kujawsko-Pomorski Agricultural Advisory Service in Minikowo
	Poland	Dolnoslaski Agricultural Advisory Service in Wrocław
	Poland	Network of Polish Chambers of Agriculture
	Poland	Network of Polish sectoral farmers associations
	Sweden	HIR – Hushållningsällskapet (consulting company within agriculture and garden)

	Switzerland	Pro Agricultura Seeland
	Switzerland	Agricultural organizations in the area of Seeland (Landwirtschaftliche Organisationen Seeland)
Policy makers at national level	Austria	Federal Ministry of Agriculture, Regions and Tourism, Austria
	France	Office Français pour la Biodiversité (French Office for biodiversity)
	France	Ministry of Agriculture
	France	Ministry of Ecological Transition
	Poland	CDR, Agriculture Advisory Centre in Brwinów- partner in the project.
	Poland	Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development
	Switzerland	Swiss Environment Agency
Influencers at European level	European Commission	Senior Policy Officer at the Directorate General of Agriculture
	European Commission	Open Method of Coordination (OMC) working groups of Member States' experts
	Joint Research Center	Knowledge Hub on Water and Agriculture
	-	Water Europe
	European Council	European Union's Standing Committee on Agricultural Research (SCAR) https://scar-europe.org/ (CDR Katarzyna Ambryszewska is a member here)
	University of Oxford	Nature-based Solutions Policy Platform https://www.nbspolicyplatform.org/

4.4 Annex 3: Template for Impact Logs

the Annex under Section 6.3. As the Impact Log grows longer, the cumulative effect can be valuable in assessing where and how the project is triggering the most direct responses, and in informing future project/programme choices. Each consortium partner is encouraged to fill in the Impact log at three points throughout the lifetime of the project (M9, M22, M44) to be able to assess changes over time.

- a. User Surveys: A more proactive way to gather information about responses to research outputs is to carry out a user survey. As this is a long-standing Monitoring & Evaluation tool, it will not be presented in detail here. However, it is relevant to note that user surveys range from large-scale questionnaire-based data gathering exercises to small focus groups. Consortium partners are encouraged to coordinate their surveying efforts since excessive use of this tool can lead to stakeholder fatigue. Surveys will be used regularly as part of the five User Engagement Workshops of WP1 and consortium members are strongly encouraged to use this opportunity for their respective interests.

The use of focus groups can in some cases be viewed as an appropriate alternative to (academic) peer review in policy research programmes, since it may be more accurate to glean the perceptions and reactions of a range of users rather than ‘experts’ when it comes to evaluating, for example, a website or a policy brief. Focus groups may be particularly useful to obtain particular views on the perceived effects of the WATERAGRI solutions on certain policies and should therefore be implemented in a targeted manner (e.g. consultation and collaboration on policy briefs, guidelines or visual development of platforms such as the serious game).

4.5 Tactics to be used by case study leads to evaluate the local impact

- a. Most Significant Change: The Most Significant Change (MSC) approach involves the collection of significant change (SC) stories, and the systematic selection of the most significant of these stories by panels of designated stakeholders or staff. This is similar to impact pathways which are advocated for and used by some of the WATERAGRI consortium members. By recording, collecting, reviewing and choosing between SC stories, staff at all levels gain greater awareness of the kinds of impacts that the project, programme or institution is working towards. This focused attention encourages a form of ongoing and indirect monitoring of the work carried out. MSC also gives a project, programme or institution a better understanding of whether and how it is achieving its purposes. In addition, it provides the project, programme or institution with a set of valuable public relations materials.
- b. Innovation Histories: A similar approach to MSC is the recording of Innovation Histories. The first step in the recording of an innovation history is for people who have been involved in the innovation to jointly construct a timeline of the innovation history, based on their recollections and on available documents. It is important to note that in order to record an innovation history, there must be a clear innovation or change to focus on. The process of

preparing this history stimulates discussion, reflection and learning amongst stakeholders. These innovation histories may be particularly useful to describe the changes that occur in the WATERAGRI case studies but may also prove interesting for marketing purposes of the WATERAGRI solution providers. As a basis for the construction of these histories, the participants can construct two or more actor matrices for selected points in the timeline to capture the dynamics of changing relationships. An example of an Actor x Actor matrix is given below (Figure 4).

	Actor A	Actor B	Actor C
Actor A		Relation of A-B	Relation of A-C
Actor B	Relation of B-A		Relation of B-C
Actor c	Relation of C-A	Relation of C-B	

1. Identify and list actors for a phase of the innovation history.
2. Actors may be NGOs, donors, etc.
3. Draw matrix describing type of relationship (collaboration, funding, etc).
4. Identify relationships that were: a) crucial; b) problematic; or c) absent but needed.

Figure 4: Example of an Actor x Actor matrix from Hovland 2017

4.6 Tactics to be used by the WATERAGRI consortium to evaluate the overall impact

The overall impact of the project will be achieved by monitoring the logframe benchmarks twice: at a mid-term review and an end review (see modular matrices below). We suggest doing an internal review by the project consortium members and an external review through the members of the Enablers Advisory Board (for more information on the role and membership of the Board refer to D9.1: Project Management Procedures and Quality Plan).

This will be complemented with collecting the individual impact logs of the consortium members and the results of surveys and focus groups as well as the MSC stories and histories of change (see above) so that proper emphasis is put on stories of *change*.

Modular Matrices: This approach is designed to help describe the internal linkages of a project or programme (Davies, 2005). The approach focuses on exploring how the components of a project or programme relate to one another; e.g., how the project's outputs relate to its desired impacts, how its outputs relate to its stakeholders, or how its outputs relate to key future events. The matrix approach that he proposes is primarily descriptive. It can therefore be a useful tool for a mid-term review, when a research project wishes to describe and assess its current status and think about how to move forward. Examples and templates of (1) an Outputs × Impacts matrix (gives the desired contribution of each project output to one or more of the project's intended impacts) (2) an Outputs × Stakeholder matrix (assesses to what degree each of the project's outputs is reaching one or more of the project's stakeholders or target audiences) are given below (Figure 5, Table 4).

Figure 9. Example of an Outputs x Impacts matrix

Impacts \ Outputs	Strengthen local research capacity on topic	Increase awareness about topic among policymakers and in media	Build relationships between research partners and civil society organisations	Influence change towards more pro-poor policy
Project launch		XXX		X
Website	X	X		X
One-on-one meetings with policymakers		XXX		XX
Public meeting series	X	X	XXX	X
Network building	XX	X	XXX	X
Research reports	XXX		X	
Policy briefs	XX	XXX	X	XX

Figure 10. Example of an Outputs x Stakeholder matrix

Stakeholders \ Outputs	Research partners	National policymakers	Bilateral and multilateral donors	Civil Society Organisations	Media
Project launch	X	XX	X	XX	XXX
Website	XX	X	XX	XX	XX
One-on-one meetings with policymakers	X	XXX			
Public meeting series	XX	X	X	XX	X
Network building	XXX		X	XXX	
Research reports	XX		X	X	
Policy briefs	X	XXX	XX	X	XX

Figure 5: Examples of how these modular matrices can look like from Hovland 2017

Table 4: Templates for the Output x Outcome and the Output x Stakeholder Matrix for the case of the WATERAGRI project

Outputs/Impacts	EU-wide and EU-country-specific agricultural policies are adapted towards sustainable agricultural food production and ecosystems in line with European bio-economy.	Agricultural water management and soil fertilisation challenges are solved in a sustainable manner to secure affordable food production in Europe for the 21st century.
Peer-reviewed journal articles in high impact journals		
Presentation (oral/keynote) at international scientific conferences (EGU, AGU, IAH, Wetpol, etc.)		
Findings are provided to global report outlets such as the World Water Development Report, UN Environment Frontiers Report, the Institute for Sustainable Development's Knowledge Hub (www.sdg.iisd.org) and others		
Presentation (oral/keynote) at global science-policy conferences and events (Stockholm Water Week, UN COPs, etc.)		
Presentation of and consultation on overarching findings to local stakeholders of case studies including local practitioners		
Trained stakeholders (including researchers)		
Use of easily digestible formats to disseminate knowledge on technical,		

political and managerial aspects for water and nutrient management		
Serving on expert boards and panels		
Position papers on international, EU-level, national and local policies as appropriate		
Policy briefs		
Practice abstracts in EIP-AGRI format		
Presentation of and consultation on overarching findings to local stakeholders of case studies including (local) policy-makers		

Outputs/Stakeholders	Policy makers at local level/municipalities	Local water management organizations	Local agricultural management organizations	Policy makers at national level	Influencers at European level	Other
Peer-reviewed journal articles in high impact journals						
Presentation (oral/keynote) at international scientific conferences (EGU, AGU, IAH, Wetpol, etc.)						
Findings are provided to global report outlets such as the World Water Development Report, UN Environment Frontiers Report, the Institute for Sustainable Development's Knowledge Hub (www.sdg.iisd.org) and others						
Presentation (oral/keynote) at global science-policy conferences and events (Stockholm Water Week, UN COPs, etc.)						
Presentation of and consultation on overarching findings to local stakeholders of case studies including local practitioners						
Trained stakeholders (including researchers)						
Use of easily digestible formats to disseminate knowledge on technical, political and managerial aspects for water and nutrient management						
Serving on expert boards and panels						
Position papers on international, EU-level, national and local policies as appropriate						
Policy briefs						
Practice abstracts in EIP-AGRI format						

Presentation of and consultation on overarching findings to local stakeholders of case studies including (local) policy-makers						
Peer-reviewed journal articles in high impact journals						

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6 Annex

6.1 Annex 1: Policies, decrees, rules or laws that WATERAGRI could influence or be influenced at various levels

Level	Country/region	Name of policy, rule, law or decree	Link (if available) to text
International	UN	United Nations Conference on Sustainable Development (Rio+20), "The Future We Want"	General Assembly resolution 67/290 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development
	UNFCCC	The Paris Agreement	https://unfccc.int/files/essential_background/convention/application/pdf/english_paris_agreement.pdf
	UNCBD	The Nagoya Protocol on Access and Benefit-sharing	https://www.cbd.int/abs/
EU	European Union	Proposal for a REGULATION OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL establishing the framework for achieving climate neutrality and amending Regulation (EU) 2018/1999 (European Climate Law)	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?qid=1588581905912&uri=CELEX:52020PC0080
	European Union	Common agricultural policy (CAP)	https://ec.europa.eu/info/food-farming-fisheries/key-policies/common-agricultural-policy_en
	European Union	The future CAP	https://ec.europa.eu/commission/sites/beta-political/files/budget-may2018-modernising-cap_en.pdf https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=COM%3A2018%3A392%3AFIN
	European Union	Effect of CAP on water	https://ec.europa.eu/info/food-farming-fisheries/key-policies/common-agricultural-policy/cmef/sustainability/impact-cap-water_en
	European Union	The EU water policy, eg. the regulation on water re-use	https://ec.europa.eu/environment/water/index_en.htm FIT4REUSE deliverable on "Inventory of the current legislative and policy frameworks addressing non-conventional water resources treatment and application" (to be made available by UNIBO in Dec. 2020).

	European Union	Commission Staff Working Document Agriculture and Sustainable Water Management in the EU	https://circabc.europa.eu/sd/a/a/bff972e-203a-4b4e-b42e-a0f291d3fdf9/SWD_2017_EN_V4_P1_885057.pdf
	European Union	Nitrates Directive	https://ec.europa.eu/environment/water/water-nitrates/index_en.html
	European Union	Drought mitigation	https://ec.europa.eu/environment/water/quantity/eu_action.htm https://ec.europa.eu/environment/water/quantity/building_blocks.htm https://europeansting.com/2020/07/21/european-union-policy-for-improving-drought-preparedness-and-mitigation/
National	Austria	Austrian Water Protection Law (Österreichisches Wasserrechtsgesetz (WRG 1959 in the actual version))	https://www.ris.bka.gv.at/GeltendeFassung.wxe?Abfrage=Bundesnormen&Gesetzesnummer=10010290
	Austria	National Water Management Plan 2021 (Nationaler Gewässerbewirtschaftungsplan 2021)	https://www.bmlrt.gv.at/wasser/wasser-oesterreich/plan_gewaesser_ngp/nationaler_gewaesserbewirtschaftungsplan-ngp/ngp_arbeitsprogramm_2018.html
	Austria	Guidelines for advisory services on water and soil protection by the Landwirtschaftskammer Österreich (Austrian Chamber of Agriculture)	https://www.lko.at/boden-wasser-schutz-beratung+2500+2515416
	France	Payments for ecosystem services (Paielements pour services environnementaux)	https://agriculture.gouv.fr/les-paiements-pour-services-environnementaux-en-agriculture https://www.actualitesdudroit.fr/browse/affaires/droit-economique/26550/paiements-pour-services-environnementaux-la-commission-approuve-le-regime-d-aide-aux-agriculteurs
	France	Nitrates and Water Directives adaptation	https://www.ecologie.gouv.fr/protection-ressource-en-eau
	Italy	Implementation of Directive 2007/60/EC on the assessment and management of flood risks (Decreto Legislativo 23 febbraio 2010 n. 49 Attuazione della direttiva 2007/60/CE relativa alla valutazione e alla gestione dei	https://www.minambiente.it/normative/dlgs-23-febbraio-2010-n-49-attuazione-della-direttiva-200760ce-relativa-alla-valutazione-e

		rischi di alluvioni. (GU del 2 aprile 2010 n. 77) Testo consolidato 2020)	
	Italy	Environmental Norm (Norma in materia ambientale; Decreto Legislativo 152 del 03/04/2006)	https://www.minambiente.it/sites/default/files/dlgs_03_04_2006_152.pdf
	Italy	Water management plan of the Po River Catchment (Piano di Gestione del distretto idrografico del fiume Po. Comitato Istituzionale del 3 marzo 2016, deliberazione n.1/2016 (DPCM 27 Ottobre 2016))	https://pianoacque.adbpo.it/piano-di-gestione-2015/
	Poland	Set of strategic national documents currently under construction in the area of water management in agriculture	

6.2 Annex 2: Initial indicative list of stakeholders that could influence policymaking

Stakeholder Category	Country	Organization
Policy makers at local level/municipalities	Austria	Provincial Government of Lower Austria
	Austria	Chamber of Agriculture of Lower Austria
	Austria	Styrian Provincial Government (Austria)
	Austria	Chamber of Agriculture of Styria (Austria)
	France	Puisaye-Forterre Municipalities Federation for Water Management (Fédération des eaux de Puisaye-Forterre)
	Italy	Municipality of Ravenna (Comune di Ravenna)
	Italy	Region of Emilia Romagna (Regione Emilia Romagna)
	Poland	Regional Agricultural Advisory Centers
	Poland	Regional and local Self-governmental authorities (regions, counties, communities)
	Sweden	Swedish Board of Agriculture (Jordbruksverket)
	Sweden	Municipality of Eslöv (Eslövs kommun)
	Switzerland	Councillor Ins (Gemeinderat Ins)
	Switzerland	Councillor Epsach (Gemeinderat Epsach)
Local water management organizations	Austria	Hydraulic engineering official expert for the district of Weiz South
	Finland	Centres for Economic Development, Transport and the Environment (ELY-centers)
	France	Yonne Regional Agency of the government (Direction Départementale du Territoire)
	France	Regional water agency (Agence de l'eau Seine Normandie)
	Italy	Po River District Basin Authority (Autorità di bacino distrettuale del fiume Po)
	Italy	Energy Resource Environment Holdings Hera (Holding Energia Risorse Ambiente,)
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	Italy	Renana Reclamation Consortium (Consorzio di Bonifica Renana)
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	Poland	Local Water Companies
	Poland	State Water Holding Polish Waters
	Sweden	Ekologigruppen – Consulting company in ecological matters
	Switzerland	Technical Commission Water of Pro Agricultura (Technische Kommission Wasser der Pro Agricultura)
	Switzerland	Water supply Grosses Moos (Wasserversorgung Grosses Moos (WAGROM))
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	Germany	Chamber of Agriculture North-rhine Westphalia (Landwirtschaftskammer Nordrhein-Westfalen)
	Hungary	Hungarian Irrigation Association
	Hungary	T-Markt Ltd.
	Hungary	MAGTÁR Ltd
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	Poland	Lubelski Agricultural Advisory Service in Końskowola
	Poland	Kujawsko-Pomorski Agricultural Advisory Service in Minikowo
	Poland	Dolnoslaski Agricultural Advisory Service in Wrocław
	Poland	Network of Polish Chambers of Agriculture
	Poland	Network of Polish sectoral farmers associations
	Sweden	HIR – Hushållningssällskapet (consulting company within agriculture and garden)

	Switzerland	Pro Agricultura Seeland
	Switzerland	Agricultural organizations in the area of Seeland (Landwirtschaftliche Organisationen Seeland)
Policy makers at national level	Austria	Federal Ministry of Agriculture, Regions and Tourism, Austria
	France	Office Français pour la Biodiversité (French Office for biodiversity)
	France	Ministry of Agriculture
	France	Ministry of Ecological Transition
	Poland	CDR, Agriculture Advisory Centre in Brwinów- partner in the project.
	Poland	Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development
	Switzerland	Swiss Environment Agency
Influencers at European level	European Commission	Senior Policy Officer at the Directorate General of Agriculture
	European Commission	Open Method of Coordination (OMC) working groups of Member States' experts
	Joint Research Center	Knowledge Hub on Water and Agriculture
	-	Water Europe
	European Council	European Union's Standing Committee on Agricultural Research (SCAR) https://scar-europe.org/ (CDR Katarzyna Ambryszewska is a member here)
	University of Oxford	Nature-based Solutions Policy Platform https://www.nbspolicyplatform.org/

6.3 Annex 3: Template for Impact Logs

 Policy Impact Logs
Date:
Name of consortium partner:
Name(s) and position(s) of involved consortium members:
Relation to WATERAGRI case study (if any):
To be filled in at the beginning of the project
Initial policy influence objectives:
What policy will be targeted?
Which entity/policy maker/stakeholder will be influenced?
What strategy/ies is/are to be used?
<i>To be filled in in the middle and at the end of the project</i>
<i>Describe the level of policy influence achieved:</i>

<i>Used strategies:</i>	
<i>Factors that facilitated influence and why:</i>	<i>Factors that obstructed influence and why:</i>
<i>Lessons learned:</i>	